

weak or no dormancy, their storage life varied widely. Viability appears to be controlled by genetic factors; dwarf indica TN1/Taichung 65 lost viability very quickly.

In general, the gradual fall of seed viability was due to the increase in relative humidity (58% to 85%), and in temperature (26 to 31°C). □

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CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils and soil characterization

Urea hydrolysis in oxidized and reduced flooded soil

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We studied urea hydrolysis in oxidized and reduced soil systems in a controlled laboratory setup (Fig. 1). Soil was an Oxisol, kaolinitic clay (Typic Haplorthox) with pH 5.2, 1.72% organic C, 0.13% N, and CEC 15.5 meq/ 100 g. It contained 56.2% clay, 11.9% silt, and 31.9% sand.

Four hundred grams of 2 mm air-dried soil (oven dry weight basis) and 1,600 ml of water were placed into a 2-liter conical flask, stirred continuously with a magnetic stirrer, and incubated in the dark at 25 °C. Stable soil redox conditions and pH were obtained by continuously purging the soil suspension with 99.9% O₂ (for oxidized conditions) or 99.9% N₂ gas (for reduced conditions) for about 30 d before adding urea. Duplicate flasks were run for urea and no N treatments.

Urea was applied at 200 mg N/ kg soil and the contents of the flasks stirred continuously, purging either with O₂ or N₂ gas. Duplicate 25-ml aliquots of soil suspensions were removed 0, 0.5, 1, 2, 4, and 7 d after adding urea. The aliquots were used to determine oven-dry soil weight and urea N.

The oxidized soil suspension was extracted with KCl-PMA solution having a final concentration of 2M. The

reduced soil suspension was extracted by preflushing the bottles with N₂; O₂-free KCl-PMA solution also was used for

extraction. The supernatant solution of the reduced soil samples was filtered under a N₂ atmosphere. The unhydrolyzed urea recovered in the KCl-PMA extracts was determined colorimetrically immediately after extraction.

1. Schematic of experimental setup used to oxidize or reduce soil in the laboratory. Louisiana State University, Baton Rouge, USA, 1988.

2. Urea hydrolyzed in oxidized and reduced flooded Sumatra soil at 25 °C. Louisiana State University, Baton Rouge, USA, 1988.

The results show that rate of urea hydrolysis in the oxidized soil proceeded at a significantly slower rate than in the reduced soil for all the incubation periods (Fig. 2). At 1 d after application, 40% of added urea was hydrolyzed in the oxidized soil, and 62% in the reduced soil. At 4 d, 72% of added urea was hydrolyzed in the oxidized soil, and 93% in the reduced soil. At 7 d, a small amount of urea still remained in the oxidized soil, but no trace was found in the reduced soil. □

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Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Influence of P, K, micronutrients, and dolomite on azolla growth

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We studied the effects of P, K, micronutrients (M), and dolomite (D) on azolla growth and its P accumulation in 1.2- × 2.3-m plots in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. The test was conducted at 1,260 m altitude at the end of the warm season Mar 1985 (air temperature 16-25 °C; water temperature 11-40 °C) in Antananarivo.

Soil was sandy clay loam mineral hydromorph, with pH 5.2, 1.13% total P, 0.155% Olsen P, 3% organic matter, 1.7% C, and ex-K 0.18 meq/100 g.

Treatments were P alone; P and K; P, K, and M; P, K, and D; and P, K, M,

and D. P was applied at 7 kg/ha as triple superphosphate, K at 5 kg/ha as KCl, and M at 10 kg/ha as a commercial cocktail containing 0.3% B, 1.5% Fe, 0.5% Cu, 1.5% Mn, 0.01% Mo, 1.5% Zn, 4% MgO, 5% N, and 5% S. Dolomite was applied at 300 kg/ha. P was applied weekly at 7 kg/ha; the other materials were applied only at the beginning of the test. Dolomite was applied to estimate the influence of pH changes.

Azolla growth and P accumulation during 37 d at the end of the warm season in 1985, Antananarivo, Madagascar.

Treatment	Azolla wt		P accumulated	
	g	Increase over control (%)	%	Increase over control (%)
Control	110	—	0.059	—
P	270	157	0.197	235
P+K	280	169	0.200	239
P+K+M	340	218	0.198	236
P+K+D	310	189	0.205	247
P+K+M+D	350	228	0.211	258
LSD (0.05)	101		0.102	

Azolla pinnata var. *pinnata* (var. *africana*) was inoculated at 50 g/plot. Azolla fresh weight and P accumulation were recorded 37 d after inoculation.

Results show that P is essential to azolla growth (see table). Fronds cultivated with P were reddish green. P-deficient fronds were reddish brown, and their roots were long and easily detached. Dolomite, micronutrients, P, and K together induced uniform azolla multiplication. K did not influence frond proliferation.

P accumulation was remarkable. Azolla incorporated as green manure could be a source of available P. □

Response of flooded rice to green manure

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We studied the relative contribution of N from aboveground (shoot) and